

POLITICAL SCIENCES

RADICALIZATION TO TERRORISM: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Nowadays, Europe is increasingly threatened by radicalization towards terrorism. Although it is not a new phenomenon, the extent of the radicalization of individuals and European citizens is reaching alarming levels. International and regional security organizations such as UN, NATO, EU, OSCE etc., are making significant efforts to prevent and combat this problem.

Keywords: *radicalization, terrorism, Europe, society, extremism, bibliometric analysis*

Introduction

The fight against terrorism has been a social and political priority for Europe since the terrorist attacks in the US on 11th of September 2001. European security policies were deeply affected by the attacks in Madrid (2004) and London (2005), which made it clear that Europe is vulnerable to terrorist threat. These attacks showed that member states should adopt common security policies that focus on the immediate prevention of such tragedies. Since most of those who committed the terrorist attacks in Europe were European citizens, the military response based only on coercive measures could no longer be effective, given the fact that most of those who committed the terrorist attacks in Europe were European citizens. This also gave birth to a new concept, the homegrown terrorism. Given this fact a reconceptualization of the field of terrorism prevention was necessary because of the new manifestations of terrorism that appeared in the 21st century.

There is a “rage” among the second or third generation of migrants towards Western policies, according to the signs sent by the competent institutions in the prevention and combating of terrorism in various European states. This led to the idea that the causes and factors that cause discontent and lead to violence and involvement in acts of terrorism must be found.

Although there is no universally accepted definition for radicalization, certainly the process of radicalization it is an early stage of involvement in terrorist actions, so in recent years, one of the main concerns of European institutions and organizations has been the prevention of radicalization for terrorist purposes. For example, starting with 2005, the European Union has adopted several strategies to combat terrorism and has taken steps to improve its ability to respond to new threats and that member states are obliged to identify concrete tools to prevent this phenomenon [1].

From the start of these events, radicalization and terrorism had been a subject of interest also for researchers and scholars, studying the psychological, social, political and military implications. The literature is in a continuous expansion, but limited to a singular perspective, region or event. Considering this fact, we

decided that in this research to elaborate an extensive analysis of the literature existing in the last ten years.

This article aims to present the most discussed topics in the research field of radicalization and terrorism in recent years, through a bibliometric analysis of the specialized literature. As said, the objective of the study is:

To conduct a bibliometric analysis of research in the field of radicalization and terrorism using a VoS viewer.

The article includes four parts. The first part – literature review – summarizes the previous findings found in studies regarding the two concepts discussed: *Radicalization* and *Terrorism*. The second part - methodology - describes the methods by which the bibliometric analysis was carried out. The third part – results and discussion - presents and discusses the main conclusions obtained through the bibliometric analysis research. The fourth part - conclusions - summarizes the article, includes implications for practice and defines the limits of the research and suggestions for future research.

Literature review

Following the terrorist attacks in Madrid (2004) and London (2005), committed for the first time by European citizens, violent radicalization is a phenomenon that began to be increasingly addressed in the specialized literature.

Radicalization include changes from moderate to radical beliefs, adopting an attitude of rejection towards society and a propensity for violent or extreme actions to advance one's ideologies. However, there is no single universal definition of radicalization.

Many institutions, international and regional organizations, scholars and professors tried to define this phenomenon as precisely as possible, but until now, there is no fully accepted and applicable definition, most likely due to the complexity, typologies, factors and different forms of manifestation of radicalization.

According to European Commission, “radicalization is a phased and complex process in which an individual or a group embraces a radical ideology or belief

that accepts, uses or condones violence, including acts of terrorism, to reach a specific political or ideological purpose” [2].

The OSCE explains radicalization that leads to terrorism as “the dynamic process whereby an individual comes to accept terrorist violence as a possible, perhaps even legitimate, course of action. This may eventually, but not necessarily, lead this person to advocate, act in support of, or to engage in terrorism”[3].

In the work *Radical, Religious and Violent: The new Economics of Terrorism*, Eli Berman applies a rational choice model to the radicalization process, demonstrating that the presence of mutual aid networks increases the resistance of radical groups. When those groups decide to use violence, they also enjoy increased lethality and are protected from defection and other forms of intervention by states and outside groups [4].

Alex Schmid defines radicalization as a process of political socialization towards extremism. Alternatively, radicalization can be viewed as a process of conflict escalation in terms of increased use of illegal methods of political action when confronting an opponent. It can also be seen as a mobilization and recruitment process, masterminded by manipulative political or religious entrepreneurs. It can finally be viewed primarily as a conversion process, a life-changing transformation from a more individual-centered personal identity to a new, collective-centered identity which makes the vulnerable individual subservient to the demands of an extremist religious cult while making him or her think of belonging to a superior group of true believers [5].

As we showed above, there is no single accepted and applicable definition of radicalization, as the idea varies by context and application. There are many viewpoints about radicalization such as religion, society, politics and psychology. There are many different definitions of radicalization by different groups and scholars.

In conclusion, most definitions of radicalization say it is a process by which a person adopts extremist attitudes, ideologies, or behaviors. These ideologies may include violence or intolerance towards other groups or individuals. They can also lead to radical changes in the way people think and behave.

The term terrorism comes from the Latin language, from the words *terror - terroris*, and has a military connotation. Terrorism, as a method of action, means the practice of terror and designates acts likely to cause in a certain environment a feeling of intense fear, harbinger of an inevitable evil.

The definition of the notion of terrorism has been carried out countless times and very diversified. Certain definitions consider this phenomenon to be normal, as a reaction to the “virsing” of societal systems and the upheaval of value systems, others place it in the extreme forms of the manifestation of human violence, and most consider it a phenomenon of social pathology, abnormal, asymmetric, even atypical reaction and, in general, completely disproportionate to progress, to the evolutionary trends of societies. Of course, these definitions have their importance, as they analyze, from various points of view, a phenomenon - the phenomenon of terrorism.

According to Directive (EU) 2017/541 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on combating terrorism, terrorist aims are described as any of the following:

- seriously intimidating a population;
- unduly compelling a government or an international organization to perform or abstain from performing any act;
- seriously destabilizing or destroying the fundamental political, constitutional, economic or social structures of a country or an international organization [6].

In *The Age of Terrorism*, Walter Laquer defines terrorism as the use or the threat of the use of violence, a method of combat, or a strategy to achieve certain targets. Terrorism aims to induce a state of fear in the victim, that is ruthless and does not conform with humanitarian rules. He also exposes publicity as an essential factor in the terrorist strategy [7].

Alex Schmid and Albert Jongman defined terrorism as an anxiety-inspiring method of repeated violent action, employed by semi-clandestine individual, group, or state actors, for idiosyncratic, criminal, or political reasons, whereby, in contrast to assassination, the direct targets of violence are not the main targets. The immediate human victims of violence are generally chosen randomly (targets of opportunity) or selectively (representative or symbolic targets) from a target population, and serve as message generators [8].

Over the time, terrorism has been given hundreds of definitions. Just like radicalization, there is no universally applicable definition of terrorism because interpretations can vary depending on the context and perspective and due to the typologies and forms of manifestation. Schmid and Jongman’s groundbreaking analysis of the discourse of terrorism definitions, which examined the frequency of terms in 109 definitions, *violence and force* had the highest frequency, at 83.5 percent, and *fear and terror* emphasized the third-highest frequency, at 51 percent [9].

Methodology

Alan Pritchard proposed the bibliometric analysis, which has since gained ground as a scientific technique for studying the chronological development of a topic from a multidisciplinary perspective [10]. Naveen Donthu, Kumar Satish and Debidutta Pattnaik claim that bibliometric analysis allows a full comprehension of a research topic, the mapping of its boundaries, the identification of significant authors, and novel directions for future research [11].

The bibliometric method was used for this study because of its ability to establish the intellectual structure of a topic objectively. This type of analysis, as well as the science mapping technique, are useful for objectively examining the evolutionary tendency of research studies and have been used successfully in past literature reviews [12]. As a result, the current study focuses on understanding how research is targeted toward contemporary trends in radicalization and terrorism in Europe, as well as the relevance of these concepts in academia worldwide.

This study intends to highlight the most popular concepts tackled by scholars in connection to radicalization and terrorism in the previous ten years, as well as to examine worldwide interest in this topic.

To meet the study's aims, we adopted a two-step process to identify the papers that would be analyzed and reviewed. The first stage was to identify appropriate search keywords for mining the Scopus and Web of Science databases for relevant papers. This database was chosen because of its vast coverage of peer-reviewed research in credible publications, as well as its

ubiquitous presence in the academic community [13]. In the second step, we employed predefined criteria to determine which papers to include in our database for bibliometric and content analysis.

To conduct this bibliometric study, the keywords “terrorism”, “radicalization” and “Europe” were used to define the base of investigated papers. In order to define the database, we used these keywords in a conducted search in both Scopus and Web of Science forming two databases used in parallel in this research.

Table 1

First step in mining the two selected databases		
	WEB OF SCIENCE	SCOPUS
SEARCHED WORDS	“terrorism”, “radicalization”, “Europe”	“terrorism”, “radicalization”, “Europe”
SEARCH WITHIN ARTICLES	All fields	Article title, Abstract, Key words
GENERATED	153	154

In the first step of the process, we also discovered the selected papers' analysis by category and distribution by year on Web of Science, as shown below. This

gives us an overview of the researchers' vision and interest in the analyzed concepts.

Figure 1 – Chart of publication distribution by years – retrieved from Web of Science

Figure 2 – Chart of publication distribution by categories – retrieved from Web of Science

According to fig. 1, the year in which researchers showed the most interest in the investigated issue is 2015, followed by the years 2020, 2022, and 2018, with the fewest publications in the years 2017 and 2013.

The second figure depicts the distribution of articles in the Web of Science categories, revealing that more than half of the publications are in the fields of Political Science (53), International Relations (33), and

Religion (32). Additional areas of note include: Criminology Penology, Sociology, Social Science Interdisciplinary and others.

To thoroughly investigate the scholarly discourse at the nexus of “radicalization” and “terrorism” in Europe, an elaborate search method was meticulously constructed. This method entailed leveraging the capacity of multiple bibliographic databases to ensure comprehensive and deep coverage of the literature. The first database, Web of Science, was used using the

search phrases “terrorism”, “radicalization”, and “Europe”, giving an initial pool of 153 articles. Concurrently, a similar search was performed in Scopus, the second database, yielding 154 first hits using the identical search criteria. Articles must have been written within the last ten years to meet the criteria for recency and relevancy. Following thorough application of these criteria, the final results were improved, yielding 131 articles from Web of Science and 129 from Scopus, which served as the foundation for the further analysis and synthesis of literature in this work.

Figure 3 – Overview of the methodology

An creative analytical technique was employed to delve further into the complex web of scholarly discourse at the intersection of terrorism and radicalization in Europe. Aside from the initial database curation, one critical step in our process was to subject the two databases, Web of Science and Scopus, to a thorough scrutiny by VOSviewer software. This sophisticated technology helps in the research of co-authorship relationships, providing critical insights into the field's collaborative dynamics. We were able to identify not only the prolific writers contributing to this discourse, but also the geographical origins of these collaborative projects, shedding light on the worldwide spread of knowledge, thanks to VOSviewer's capabilities.

In addition, our analytical methods extended beyond authorship analysis. VOSviewer was used to interpret the complexity of keyword co-occurrence, exposing the key concepts and thoughts that underlie the material being studied. This multifaceted approach highlighted not just the collaborative networks and international aspects of terrorism and radicalization research, but also the key topics and concepts that create this intellectual landscape. Our research aims to provide an in-depth view and comprehensive understanding of the relationship between terrorism and radicalization in Europe by combining these various parts of analysis and drawing on the collective experience of researchers and practitioners worldwide.

Results and discussions

The following section serves as a starting point for a more in-depth examination of the findings and subsequent discussions that emerged from an exhaustive bibliometric analysis in our pursuit of a comprehensive understanding of the complex academic literature at the intersection of radicalization and terrorism in Europe. The study, which was precisely coordinated utilizing VOSviewer software, adds to the academic debate by emphasizing the intricate structures of collaboration as well as the essential theme foundations within this conceptual dimension.

The preceding sections outlined the methodological planning, which involved carefully integrating two major bibliographic databases, Web of Science and Scopus, to generate a representative corpus of current and relevant research. The subsequent use of

VOSviewer software provides a comprehensive lens, providing insight into the evolution of this discourse through co-authorship analysis and illustrating the shifting character of intellectual discussion through keyword co-occurrence mapping.

The concepts delivered here go beyond simple statistical abstractions. They serve as the foundation for the creation of a knowledge framework. This research provides for a complete comprehension of recent conversation as well as the development of a future roadmap. As a result, this study presents researchers' perspectives on radicalization and terrorism in Europe, providing an overview of the concepts and serving as the foundation for further in-depth and on-the-ground research on how local politics and methods to prevent radicalization intersect in the context.

Figure 4- Co-occurrence - Web of Science database

Source: Authors capture from VOSviewer

The Web of Science database underwent a thorough co-occurrence analysis using the VOSviewer software. Initially, our analysis found 460 different keywords. To assure the relevance and significance of the detected keywords, a minimum occurrence threshold of 4 was established, reducing the keyword pool to 31 terms that matched this condition. Following that, a thorough evaluation was performed, removing terms that appeared in similar forms while maintaining those that had the strongest semantic relationships within the dataset. This thorough curating resulted in a consistent

co-occurrence map that artistically captured the complex interactions between the selected terms. Remarkably, the generated map revealed a structured landscape divided into four unique clusters, each representing a specific theme domain. The visual representation of this map (Fig. 4), which we show in the following section, is an excellent resource for understanding the intricate interplay of ideas and concepts that constitute the discourse on the intersection of terrorism and radicalization within the Web of Science database.

Figure 5 - Co-occurrence - Scopus database

Source: Authors capture from VOSviewer

The Scopus database, like its Web of Science counterpart, underwent a thorough co-occurrence analysis aided by VOSviewer software. This study initially yielded a vast corpus of 592 distinct terms. To ensure precision and salience in our study, we adopted a strict minimum occurrence criteria of four. Because of this sensible application, the keyword pool was narrowed to 25 phrases that exceeded the predetermined level. Following that, an intricate keyword validation approach was performed with the purpose of deleting duplicates

and retaining only those with significant semantic relationships within the dataset. This meticulous curating procedure resulted in the creation of an enlightening co-occurrence map that captured the intricate network of keyword associations. This map depicts an ordered landscape divided into four clusters, each containing a distinct thematic component. Figure 5 depicts this map graphically, giving as a visual key to understanding the complex interaction of ideas and concepts that form up the field of radicalization and terrorism inside the Scopus database.

Table 2

Comparison of the first keywords from the databases

WEB OF SCIENCE			SCOPUS			
	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
1	Radicalization	61	190	Terrorism	67	214
2	Terrorism	63	190	Radicalization	39	115
3	Europe	21	84	Human	16	108
4	Extremism	16	61	Europe	20	95
5	Security	11	49	Violence	12	74
6	Education	12	48	Extremism	16	44
7	Violence	9	39	Adolescent	5	41
8	Poverty	10	36	Psychology	5	41
9	War	9	36	Ideology	6	38
10	Islam	10	35	Risk assessment	5	35
11	Counterterrorism	6	32	Islam	8	34
12	Youth	6	27	Mental disease	5	34
13	Identity	6	26	European Union	9	32
14	European Union	7	24	Security	8	32
15	Jihadism	5	22	Jihadism	9	27

As we delve deeper into the co-occurrence analysis of terms in the Web of Science and Scopus databases, it becomes clear that minor differences in the definition of thematic clusters may arise. This variance might be attributable to the databases' distinct makeup and emphasis, as well as the continually changing nature of research trends. While such discrepancies may appear to be a problem at first, they actually give an enormous opportunity for scholarly discourse and future research.

Certain keywords emerge from these large groupings, with important implications for future study on the interface of radicalization and terrorism. The terms “extremism”, “violence”, “education”, “ideology”, “Islam”, “jihadism”, “counterterrorism” and “European Union” stand out among these. These categories indicate critical research pathways and imply that studying the complex interplay of these qualities has immense promise for improving our understanding of how to

properly respond with new ways to prevent and counter radicalization. The bibliometric analysis of co-authorship revealed important insights into the landscape of radicalization and terrorism, notably about authors and countries. According to the research, European countries, especially United Kingdom, Netherlands, France and Belgium, alongside the United States of America have the most publications on terrorism and radicalization, proving their significant contributions to the field. Several other European countries, including Spain, Germany and Italy, have conducted considerable study in this area. The analysis identified a proportion of notable researchers from Australia, Canada, Pakistan and Singapore, underscoring the global nature of the researched topic. These findings illustrate the various perspectives and collaborations that exist across continents, providing insights into the cross-cultural flow of information and perspectives in the researched field.

Figure 6- Co-authorship country - Web of Science database

Source: Authors capture from VOSviewer

Figure 7 - Co-authorship by country - Scopus database

Source: Authors capture from VOSviewer

Table 3

Comparative data of co-authorship by country								
Web of Science				Scopus				
	Country	Documents	Citations	Total link strength	Country	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
1	Netherlands	16	216	17	UK	25	176	10
2	England	14	112	14	France	10	142	6
3	USA	40	142	13	Netherlands	13	213	6
4	Belgium	5	15	12	Australia	5	33	4
5	France	10	63	11	Sweden	4	24	4
6	Scotland	3	71	8	USA	16	146	4
7	Finland	4	6	6	Germany	11	143	3
8	Pakistan	3	1	6	Belgium	4	7	2
10	Spain	17	48	6	Italy	17	67	2
11	Australia	3	7	5	Spain	8	32	2
12	Italy	7	13	5	Austria	4	0	1
13	Canada	3	6	4	Canada	4	6	1
14	Turkey	3	0	4	Singapore	3	26	1
15	Russia	6	34	2	Finland	4	6	0
16	Sweden	6	34	2	Russia	4	2	0
17	Germany	11	84	1	-	-	-	-

Our bibliometric analysis exposes the fact that many researchers believe that radicalization is a factor that can contribute to the susceptibility of individuals to engage in violent or terrorist behavior. This process can involve an ideological and emotional transformation of the individual towards an extremist or radical view, which can justify or even promote violence in the name of a cause.

As well, in the specialized literature, there are different models and theories that try to explain the relationship between radicalization and terrorism, as well as the ways to prevent and manage these phenomena. Some studies focus on the analysis of individual and collective factors that influence the radicalization process, while others examine the role of the online environment, the influence of social groups, and the dynamics of radical groups in the formation of terrorist behavior.

Conclusions

To summarize, radicalization is a process of developing extremist beliefs, emotions, and behaviors. Extremist beliefs are deeply held beliefs that oppose the fundamental values of society, the laws of democracy and universal human rights by supporting the supremacy of a particular group (racial, religious, political, economic, social, etc.). Extremist emotions and behaviors can be expressed both through non-violent pressure and coercion, and through actions that deviate from the norm and show contempt for life, liberty and human rights.

In the specialized literature, there are different models and theories that try to explain the relationship between radicalization and terrorism, as well as the ways to prevent and manage these phenomena. Some studies focus on the analysis of individual and collective factors that influence the radicalization process, while others examine the role of the online environment, the influence of social groups, and the dynamics of radical groups in the formation of terrorist behavior.

As well, in many articles available in open sources, radicalization is often associated and seen as a precursor to terrorism. But this is not always true because there are people who share radical ideologies, but they do not engage in acts of terrorism. It is important to emphasize that not all those who are radicalized become terrorists and that there are many factors that can influence this process, including the social, economic, political and personal context of the individual. We also need to be aware of the diversity of contexts and reasons that can lead to involvement in terrorism.

The danger represented by radicalization towards terrorism is not completely eliminated, because anyone can grab a kitchen knife and stab a stranger on the street or drive a car into a crowd of people. No government, not even a totalitarian one, can stop persons, especially mentally ill and suicidal persons, from doing so [14].

However, the effort made by the EU in the field of preventing and combating this threat must be noted. Due to the measures imposed such as information exchange, cutting off terrorist financing, firearms control, digitalization of judicial cooperation, cooperation with non-EU countries etc., the number of terrorist attacks foiled and failed in Europe has been increasing in recent years.

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